
The Communicative Language Teaching and Students' Vocabulary Memorizing Improvement: A Library Research

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Abstract

CLT is one of the techniques used to improve students' ability to learn vocabulary. Apart from memorizing vocabulary, students are also expected to be able to use vocabulary to communicate with one another, both indoors and outdoors. The type of research used by researchers is library research. This study aims to determine the development of learning using the CLT technique on vocabulary which was carried out in previous years, from 2008 to 2019. The samples taken were five articles, namely two published journal articles, two regular articles that were unpublished and one thesis. as well as researchers using qualitative methods to analyze some of these articles. The type of data used by researchers is document data. Following the data and results analyzed by the researcher, it can be said that learning using the CLT technique on vocabulary is not effective if it only relies on vocabulary without combining all the skills (Listening, Reading, Writing and Speaking) that exist in language learning. Therefore, if teachers want CLT learning to Vocabulary to be effective, then all the skills in the language must be combined so that the achievement of the desired results can be realized.

Keywords: *CLT, Vocabulary, Memorizing, Vocabulary Memorizing, Advantage and Disadvantage of CLT, Difficulties in Teaching and Learning Vocabulary.*

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1. Introduction

Language is one of the communication tools used by individuals against individuals, individuals towards society, and society to society. In the use of language, there are several skills used, namely; reading, speaking, listening and writing, the four skills encourage one another. However, in this research, the researcher did not research by taking one of the four skills but, the researcher only referred to one language element, namely the vocabulary. This

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type of research conducted by researchers is a research library. In this study, there are several items analyzed by the researcher as samples that will determine the use of CLT on students' vocabulary while in the classroom.

The purpose of communicative learning is to shape students' language skills and communication skills (Delvia, 2017). So, if learning a language means that it is inseparable from communication between students, teachers, and the community to convey their aims and objectives, then language learning must be under the level of use so that it can be understood, by those invited to speak or the interlocutor.

In research related to CLT, much has been studied by previous researchers, let alone research on language in general. Thus, the teaching of CLT had been many researchers had stated that it is perfect when applied in the classroom, but if there could be other studies that have put forward things that are contrary to what was conveyed by several researchers discussed below.

According to Devianty (2016), learning communicative means that it is easy to implement because communicative is a necessity of learned process carried out by the teacher. He also said that two things must be considerate in language teaching namely: first, language teaching for preparation as a linguist, second language teaching for language skill and communication, then learning the language is not only about being able to communicate but how we learned the language. It also can be an expert on the language what we learned. According to Littlewood (2002: 1, in Febriyanti, 2017) says that:

"The method of Communicative Language Teaching is one of the most characteristic features of communicative language teaching is that it pays systemic attention to functional as well as structural aspects of language, combining these into a more fully communicative view."

As have been researched by previous researchers that CLT has been perfecting in the learning process of students in the classroom, but previous researchers referred to language in general but not specifically language, namely vocabulary. Therefore, the researcher wants to continue researching CLT, but more specifically on the process of using vocabulary used by students while in the classroom.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

1.2.1 Does CLT improves students' vocabulary?

1.2.2 Do studies in the previous year have a close relationship with Vocabulary teaching using CLT?

2. Literature Review

2.1 *Understanding of Communicative Language Teaching*

CLT is one of the language teaching approaches used by teachers to motivate and encourage students to use the language according to the targets needed by students according to their abilities (Sotlikova and Surigin 2016). According to Harmer (2017: 84), CLT underlines that it is more important to language functions than Grammar and Vocabulary. Another opinion of Richards and Schmidt (Hertika 2013: 2, in Kusumawati and Sari 2019) says that CLT is a second approach or second language teaching that emphasizes the purpose of language learning against communicative processes used to find meaning language and communication needed by teachers and students while in the classroom. Methods of CLT According to Littlewood (2002:1, in, Febriyanti 2017) one of the features of CLT is that it gives systematic attention to aspects of language that connect to new communication.

From some of the definitions above, it can be concluded that the teaching process using the CLT method is very effective when applied in the classroom, because the target language used can be met when using CLT. Then Communicative Language Teaching is considered more important than Grammar when used for communication. Not only that, but CLT also have an influence on students' attention while following the learning process in class.

2.1.1 *Studies on Communicative Language Teaching from Year to year*

Below are some descriptions related to previous research on Communicative Language Teaching from year to year that has been researched.

Syarifuddin said that it is clear that CLT has a good influence on teachers and students in Indonesia, but CLT also has several weaknesses that are still inherent in CLT itself. However, it does not mean that CLT cannot be applied by teachers in Indonesia, but teachers must also adjust their teaching according to the context in Indonesia.

In the research, Fariady said that there were already several activities listed in the textbook, including speaking activities, vocabulary, listening activities and structural activities. Although this textbook still requires structural refinement so that teaching does not stand out too much into grammar, for that to make teaching more communicative, for the author of literature the teacher must emphasize inductive and modified grammar teaching.

This research was conducted by Budiarmo on two schools, namely SMK and SMP Mandiri Bojonggede, located in Kedung Waringin Village, Bojonggede District, Bogor Regency, on teaching CLT with the following results:

The teachers can improve their ability in speaking English; this can be seen through their rapid mechanical conversations using practice, meaningful practice and communicative practice;

Those teachers can use English following the context and can apply it in everyday use;

CLT is also able to increase the motivation and creativity of teachers in their teaching process;

It is able to provide a new atmosphere and experience for English teachers in the teaching process and increase their language proficiency actively and creatively;

This research was conducted to improve the English language skills of teachers in mechanical practice, meaningful practice and communicative practice in communicating actively and creatively.

Nuby, Rashid, Rashed. Rahman and Hasan (2020) said that it would be good to introduce CLT based learning to the curriculum at the high school level in Bangladesh because it could provide opportunities for teachers and students to improve their language skills, especially their English. However, CLT cannot be applied to rural areas according to the method used by Richards and Rogers because it has the following problems:

1. Teachers should be given specialized training and more, not only about CLT pedagogy but also about their English proficiency.
2. Teachers and students must also be involved in the system of providing information to each other, communicating and exchanging ideas so that they are motivated together in the teaching and learning process.
3. For CLT learning, classrooms must be equipped with the tools needed so that learning goes as desired together.
4. The main objective of CLT learning is communication. So the thirsty teachers can manage the classroom well, for example, being able to maintain their listening relationship so that students don't feel afraid when communicating or talking.

2.1.2 The advantages and disadvantages of CLT

Based on the results of research on CLT, there are several advantages and disadvantages of this research. Among them can be described as follows:

2.1.2.1 The Advantages of CLT

There are several advantages of CLT, including:

Cynthia and Cahyana argued that the CLT method had increased when it was used in learning. Given that the scores obtained by the participants were in the sufficient category. So in general it can be said that the participants' average score has increased so that it is included in the high category. Because the score for their perceptual aspect is 76%, it can be concluded that the score of the PQEC Institute course participants after following the CLT method has jumped significantly, especially in terms of communication.

According to WU (2009) CLT is very significant in helping to improve learning strategy skills and building conscious communication to expand the vocabulary area of students, then strengthen vocabulary towards speaking, reading, writing skills will improve and communicative skills will also be improved.

2.1.2.2 The Disadvantages of using CLT

There are several disadvantages of CLT including:

According to Diana (2014) two factors cause a misunderstanding of the use of CLT. The first is internal factor, where these factors happen to the teacher themselves because they are reluctant to improve their abilities and lack of communication with students. The second is external factors, namely the lack of training provided to teachers; lack of research resources on the teaching process and low salaries for teachers can also affect the use of CLT.

Subaidi and Haryanto (2015) compare between Communicative Technique or Explanation Technique and CLT so teaching using Communicative Technique or Explanation Technique (presenting games, songs, mas or picture) can make students interested and not bored while in the classroom. While learning using CLT for writing, speaking and reading still uses language teaching elements such as Structure / Grammar or Vocabulary which are applied in Indonesia which are modified from teaching English. So they say that teaching using Communicative Technique or Explanation Technique is more effective than CLT.

Syarifuddin (2017) said that CLT still has several principles of weakness in the Indonesian context, where CLT must be adapted in the Indonesian context. This does not mean that teachers do not need to implement all CLT in the classroom. Teachers can use CLT as their approach, but it is used in the Indonesian context.

According to Febriani (2019), teachers need to plan the learning process for students in advance based on their level of ability in the classroom. This is because the implementation of CLT is found in vocabulary research and Pronunciation is the highest-ranking from the speaking test results. Other constraints include feeling nervous, restless and a sense of self-doubt. The achievement in speaking will increase if the use of CLT by the teacher in the classroom is very effective.

2.1.3 Implementation of CLT in the Classroom

In the process of using CLT, Richard divides the learning activities into three parts, namely:

2.1.3.1 Mechanical Practice

At this stage, the teacher provides material in the form of vocabulary as an initial meeting to students as memorization material. Given, because vocabulary, in English sometimes has the same words but different meanings, it is necessary to explain also by the teacher about its use so that students do not use it, especially on vocabulary.

2.1.3.2 Meaningful Practice

Meaningful Practice is the second stage, where the learning process is that students are allowed to choose vocabulary to use when speaking, because in this stage several vocabulary classes have been given by the teacher, for example, verbs, nouns, adjectives and adverbs according to the context, which will be delivered by the teacher.

2.1.3.3 Communicative Practice

The third stage, students will be divided into several groups and will be asked to convey what they want to talk, then from the delivery, the teacher can see how much vocabulary the students have memorized and the use of vocabulary in the sentences used, whether the use of verbs, adjectives, nouns, or adverbs.

2.2 *Understanding Vocabulary*

Vocabulary is the basis of all languages used in communication, because to embrace into a sentence and then become a paragraph one must start with the vocabulary. So Wilkins says that only a little can be conveyed if the Grammar is not understood, but nothing can be conveyed if the Vocabulary is not known (Yu, 2011). Like what Wilkins said that we can convey our intentions and goals even if a little but can be conveyed clearly even though the Grammar is not very understood, but if our vocabulary is not sufficient or there are no words that we do not have, then nothing is the same, once our goals and objectives are conveyed.

Vocabulary is very important because, without vocabulary, sentences have no meaning. According to Charthy (in Lestari, 2016) said that:

“No matter how successfully the sounds of second language are mastered, without words to express a wide range of meanings, communication in second language just cannot happen in any meaningful way. And yet vocabulary often seems to be the least systematized and the least well catered for of all the aspects of learning a foreign language”.

When we use various kinds of sentences even at the paragraph level, it is inseparable from the vocabulary which is often used in communicating all the time. Vocabulary has an important role to be known and memorized and then used in everyday life to complement each other in providing information to one another so that information does not go one way but has reciprocity from the interlocutor. Therefore, vocabulary is very important to learn because, without vocabulary, it is difficult for us to communicate, remembering that we as social beings, we need vocabulary so that we can build relationships with other people in communicating, especially as a vocabulary student is needed because vocabulary is the basis of all skills. According to Faleet and Keshta (in Mirnawati, Regina and Susilawati) said that vocabulary is part of the language needed by students to communicate effectively and is the basis of all skills.

Ur (in Sariyati 2017: 43) defines that the words that are often taught by us in the foreign language learning process. However, Pribilova (2006, in suriyati, 2017: 43) states that vocabulary is not only focused on one word, but some have more than one word but have a

meaning as a single word. For example, in the use of the words post office, mother in law and look for are words that have more than one word but have one meaning, we often use it faithfully.

Actually, in learning vocabulary, several kinds of learning can be learned by students such as; single words, set of phrases, variable phrases, phrasal verbs and idioms described by Folse (2008, in Suriyati, 2017: 43-44) as follows:

a. Single words

Single words are a category of words that we often use in our daily lives and can be used in any language vocabulary as long as we have someone to talk to. Single words include room, bedroom and dining room. Of the three examples, even though the dining room has two words, it is included in one word because it expresses the same concept as room and bedroom.

b. Set phrases

This set of word type phrases not only has one word but more than one word and is always changing but cannot be used in reverse even though it has similarities when viewed from semantics. For example, on the other hand, we cannot reverse it to be in the other hand or in other hands or in other fingers. Another example is when we use the words now and then instead of then and now.

c. Variable phrases

Variable phrases are words that have several components and several variations in common that we often use in communicating. These components among are personal pronouns, possessive adjectives and word orders. For example, if in the use of the variable phrases *it has come to our attention that*, we can change the word of *our* to a possessive adjective to *my*, the same thing happens with the off and on phrases which can be changed to on and off. Thus the sentences we use are like; *it has been raining irregularly* can be changed to *it's been raining off and on* or also *it's been raining on and off*.

d. Phrasal verbs

Phrasal verbs or commonly known as phrasal have two or three particles which we often use. The first word is used in the form of a verb, while the second and third words usually use a particle word. There are many verbs used in these phrasal verbs, for example, take, go, come, get, call and put. Phrasal verbs also have nine particles that combine with the verb to form unique words, and the nine particles are *up, down, on, off, in, out, away, back* and *over*. For example, in the formation of phrasal verbs such as *take-off, take on, take down, take away, take back* and *take over*, it is a combination of phrasal verbs and particles from the phrasal verbs themselves. Generally, the quality and frequency of phrasal verbs are a little difficult to understand for students especially those studying English plus each one is very Polysemous, which means that the words have different meanings from one another. For example in the use of the basic verb take. *He took off his sweater, his career took off, the jet took off* and *I'm going to take off*. So, even though

using the same root verb but because it has different particles, the meaning of the sentences is also different according to the particle.

e. Idioms

Each language contains idioms that vary depending on the language itself. Every word or sentence can be called an idiom if the meaning of the word or sentence has a different meaning from the overall meaning. For example, *a person let the bout of the bag*, which means someone has revealed the problem, not someone has taken a cat out of his bag.

2.2.1 *The Difficulties in Teaching and Learning Vocabulary*

Below are the difficulties in learning and teaching stated by previous researchers

a. Difficulties of teaching vocabulary

It is related to previous research that vocabulary teaching will be problematic if teachers are unsure of their way of teaching and do not know how to form learning that emphasizes vocabulary learning (Berne and Blachowich 2008). Then some teachers and students also agree that the acquisition of vocabulary is the central point of teaching Walters language 2004 (in Susanto 2017).

b. Difficulties in learning vocabulary

Based on the theories put forward by the researchers, there are several difficulties faced by students in learning vocabulary. The first is that almost all students have difficulty in pronouncing vocabulary, how to write and spell the vocabulary, and in a structured arrangement are also one of the difficulties of student learning about vocabulary. Students also find it difficult to determine the meaning of the right sentence and are still confused about using it in the context and the last is that students feel confused when they find words or expressions of an expression (Rohmatilla, 2014).

2.2.2 *Assessing Students of Vocabulary*

Using a good vocabulary will lead us to a good and successful communication process towards standardizing the test. Vocabulary teaches students in their first language as well as students learning a second language. The use of assessing students' vocabulary is different, depending on the student's test objectives. For example, on assessing student vocabulary which is listed below:

- a. Define the word One way to assess the vocabulary is that students are asked to define words. This means that if the teacher provides a list of words that will be learned by students, students will easily memorize new words given by the teacher.

b. Use in Context

Moreover, the use of assessing vocabulary provides where students can use the vocabulary properly according to the context, or recognize and see the definition in the context.

2.2.2.1 There are several methods of assessment used by teachers, namely:

a. Limited response

This test is usually used by beginners to refer to an object or answer simple questions such as "yes" or "no" or express simple statements such as "raise your hand"

b. Multiple-choice completion the method of this test is where words are omitted and then students are asked to remove one lot of the correct answers according to them. There are four portions of the answer that have been prepared by the teacher and students are asked to choose one of them.

c. Multiple-choice paraphrase In this test one word has been underlined by the teacher, then students are asked to choose one of the four portions of the answer that has been provided.

Where the underlined word has the same meaning or is close to one of the four portions of the answer.

d. Simple-completion words

In this section, some words are missing, and then students are asked to put the words aside with the words they think are correct.

2.3 *The use of memorizing*

Therefore, memory must be strengthened so that the learning process in students is also more effective. Given that there are certain times when students can remember what the teacher said, and vice versa, sometimes students cannot remember and store the information conveyed by the teacher for quite a long time. This does not mean that the student's brain capacity is not able to store information, but because he does not understand the ability of the brain to memorize learning. So, there are students who respond quickly and save all the information conveyed by the teacher and there are also some students who are not quick to respond to and store this information for a long time. This is consistent with what Lorayne (2008, in Nirmalasari 2011) says that there are people who quickly remember information but don't keep it for a long time, due to a lack of empowerment of memory.

The purpose of memorizing learning is to strengthen the brain's ability to be more efficient in learning. With memorizing, the brain will always work and it will make the brain work automatically in uncovering every problem that often occurs in our daily lives. When the brain is working, there will be a shift in thinking from the conscious mind to the

subconscious mind to make the nerves of the brain better because the connections of these nerves will be thicker and work properly. Thus, we will be happier and always happier when thinking about pleasant things compared to things that are annoying or disliked, James (in Nirmasari 2011). However, several strategies can be used as a concept to improve our memory skills in the learning process. According to Lorayne and Luke (in Nirmasari 2011: 182-183) some of these concepts are:

2.3.1 Awareness

Before remembering the things that happened to us, one thing we must first remember is "important observations to bring up true awareness" so that the things around us or that are conveyed by teachers to students will be remembered and it is difficult to remember forgotten.

2.3.2 Association

In this process, when the teacher wants to provide information, the teacher should first associate it so that what is said can be remembered well. For example, when the teacher wants to repeat the spelling of the piece, the teacher must first give a piece of cake so that the students' memory can remember what they have learned before. This example is taken from an example made by Nirmasari.

2.3.3 System link

This system applies according to the continuity of two ideas with one another and so on.

2.3.4 Ridiculous association

Association is a basic form of memory whose powers can be shaped and enlarged according to situations that are obvious and funny or absurd. There are several ways to form funny or ridiculous associations. First apply the replacement rules, for example when you have a car and gloves, then draw the gloves driving the car. The second can apply unbalanced rules or reverse the real thing, for example, describing a large baseball glove driving and the third is exaggerating the rules and actions that are specific to numbers, for example, describing the millions of gloves lined up on top of street and parade.

2.3.5 Pronoun system

This pronoun system is a system used to describe something that cannot be seen with the naked eye but can be known through the mind. For example, to mention the word A, students only look for sounds that are close to A or the material, although abstract, can be described in the mind.

2.3.6 Keywords

This system only has one word to present one idea or several ideas which are longer subordinate and usually only abstract, so it must require a dressing system to be explained before creating a memorized image.

2.4 Vocabulary Memorizing

From some of the definitions listed above, it can be said that vocabulary memorizing is a learning process that prioritizes the memorization of new vocabulary that is encountered during learning. The point is that when learning is taking place, students are also required to experience their memorization ability of new vocabulary words that are heard and will be asked back by the teacher to ensure their level of memorization of vocabulary which is the teacher's goal to master the students' brains quickly and responsively in remembering new vocabulary spoken by the teacher.

There are several ways used to improve memorizing vocabulary learning delivered by Purwati (2017: 47-49) in her thesis, which are as follows:

a. Reading

Reading is an easy way to improve our vocabulary memorizing apart from enriching and expanding our vocabulary. With reading, we will find a lot of new vocabulary and we will memorize it because usually in reading there will be repeated words that usually describe an object and it is very helpful to remind this vocabulary.

b. Understand context

To understand a word, understanding the context is also needed to make it easier for us to know the word. In English, one word has many meanings so that mastery of the context of the word is also very important so that the use of language is also following it's grammatically.

c. Related words

In the use of language, the relationship between words also needs to be arranged so that it matches the meaning of a sentence that the other person wants to convey.

d. Make sentences

Make tenses are also a way to better understand new vocabulary because by writing the many words that we will use in the writing and can improve our memorization skills because besides we read we also use them. To make it even stronger, we use several sentences but have different concepts so that our knowledge and memorization of vocabulary can be expanded and widened and many vocabulary words will be used in each sentence.

e. Record yourself

By recording ourselves it will also increase our vocabulary, especially in listening to the words made by our interlocutors, our brains also unconsciously respond to memorizing the city of words that the speaker said.

f. Make a flashcard

By using flashcards, our brains are always felt to memorize vocabulary words that have been written down by ourselves, especially when they are attached to places that we always visit all the time, so our brains always receive words that we have seen intentionally or unintentionally.

g. Take notes

This method we can do to fill the time we have when travelling, so our brains always work by looking at these notes so the brain is always in its position, which is working.

h. Play games

It is also an effective trick to strengthen our memorization ability because the brain does not feel the burden when studying. With the game a lot of new vocabulary that we will get and will quickly memorize by us.

i. Speaking

Speaking also helps to find new vocabulary and we memorize it quickly because the vocabulary that is memorized is then used more quickly than memorizing but rarely used, the vocabulary will disappear by itself.

These are some of the ways that can be used to help improve our vocabulary memorizing skills over time.

3. Methods

3.1 Research design

The method used by researchers is the Qualitative method. The qualitative method according to Creswell (in Raco, 2010: 7) said that one of process approach refers to the provision of data to understand a symptom in central. Where the research used is to analyze journal articles that have been conducted by previous researchers. Ormond and Williams (in Apuke, 2017) explain that the research method is the first step to starting research.

From the above definition, it can be said that research using qualitative methods is a method used by researchers as a first step in analyzing journal articles that have been previously researched. Where, this research also functions to measure students' ability to understand their learning by using CLT against vocabulary so that researchers use this method.

This method is used by researchers because in measuring students' abilities, the method that can be used is to compare one article to another to find out how effective it is in using CLT to Vocabulary. By analyzing, the student size can be known because there are articles from previous researchers conducted before they can be used as a reference for comparison that will be used by researchers. The reference for measuring the level of student ability will be explained in the results in the next chapter.

In the design that will be used by researchers is to analyze journal articles. In the journals that will be analyzed, only five journals are the results of previous researchers. From the data that has been analyzed, it will then be made again in a graph to make it easier for researchers to return to see the effect of the CLT learning process on the vocabulary that has been previously studied.

3.2 Sample and Population

3.2.1 Sample

Arikunto (in Mirza 2016) said that the sample is a number limitation of population elements which are representative of the population itself. The samples taken by the researcher are five journal articles.

3.2.2 Population

Sugiyono (in Susilana) said that population is a general area consisting of subjects or objects that have the quantity and characteristics that have been determined by the researcher to study and draw conclusions. The population used by researchers is to analyze journals that have been researched by previous researchers from 2008 to 2019.

3.4 Technique of data Collection

3.4.1 Documentation

Documents are writings that contain important information written by hand such as information as well as written electronically, such as printed media. From these data techniques, Patton (in Raco 2010: 110-111) presents three types of data, namely: First, data obtained from in-depth interviews using open-ended questions. Second, data obtained through observations (observation) and Third, namely data obtained through documents.

3.5 The Technique of data analysis

The data analyzed by the researcher were in the form of documents. The technique is that the researcher will be analyzed the articles read one by one, then sort the articles from year to year. In these articles, the researcher will compare one article with another to find the results which are the main objective of the researcher, namely to determine the use of CLT techniques in vocabulary teaching from year to year.

When the data collection already exists, the researcher combines all of the data then summarizes the results of the data and draws conclusions on what has been analyzed and makes an accurate conclusion.

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1 Finding

Articles are obtained from previous researches as discussed below.

4.1.1 Erwan (2008)

The first research was conducted by Erwan at SMUN. 1 Ciputat, Jl. Education No. 59 on April 04 to 12 2008 with a population of 70 students from two classes, namely class X4 and class X6. Not only field data were obtained by researchers but also using library data and interviews from the English teacher at SMAN 1 Tangerang Banten and two X grade students where they were in class X4 and X6. This research emphasizes the use of Communicative Language Teaching for learning and teaching, and to find out how the Communicative Language Teaching approach is and how students react when learning Vocabulary using the Communicative Language Teaching approach.

In the learning and teaching process at SMAN 1 Ciputat, it has several principles, namely that the material and assignments have been prepared through instruction from students. The material provided by the teacher was then ended by the students with a discussion and also explained again by the teacher according to the material path.

The learning and teaching process at SMAN.1 Ciputat was carried out for two meetings. The first meeting was on Saturday, April 5, 2008, at 07.00 am, where the researcher together with the English teacher entered the X6 classroom and observed the teacher, from the books used to the teaching methods. The researcher then said that the book used was also objective because it referred more to the speaking ability to remember, it was also used for courses.

The first meeting held by the teacher was to say Assalamualaikum and followed by saying good morning and starting with hot news questions that occurred that day, in the form of natural disasters, politics, and news about celebrities and so on. One of the students began to respond by delivering news about poverty in Indonesia. With this response, there has been an interaction between the teacher and the researcher seeing the hard work made by students in responding to the question. The teacher appreciates the students by using the phrase "you are very smart". With that sentence, of course, students' self-confidence and learning motivation can increase.

Furthermore, the students were divided into nine groups with an average of four people. The student learning process is continued by the teacher when asking one student to get a newspaper published by the Jakarta Post which will be explained by the teacher first. Therefore, students are asked to find the subject of the text that was read and look for new-heard vocabulary or vocabulary that is difficult, to be discussed and in paraphrase. After that, each of the groups will explain the results that have been determined and the other groups prepare to ask what if they don't understand what the group explains. The researcher is silent

and observes how the learning process in the classroom is taking place, where the researcher does not want to engage in the discussion and see how the teacher is a good facilitator for the students.

After all, groups have presented the main text that the students want to present, the teacher continues to write down ten vocabulary words that the students already know on the board and ask them to return to explain according to the instructions from the teacher. When the students finished explaining, the teacher revised their learning results again and provided learning motivation for the students. They followed by recording the attendance of students while saying Assalamualaikum and good morning then leaving the classroom.

The second meeting, the same thing was done by the teacher, namely saying Assalamualaikum and good morning. Then the teacher returns to review the material of the last week's meeting and continues with the material that will be discussed in this second meeting. Before continuing the study, first, a story with the theme of friendship is told. The story was taken from Erwan's thesis.

Once upon a time, two young men were passing through the desert. While in the middle of the trip, one of the two boys slapped the one. The young man who was slapped was silent and did not say a word. Then the young man who was slapped walked away silently and began to write on the sand with the words "I was slapped in the face". Not long before, the two of them continued their journey. After being in the middle of the trip, the young man who was slapped had an accident because he fell into the ground and was quickly pulled by the ground. At the same time, his friend as quickly as possible helped to pull him away after being successfully pulled, he moved away and returned to carving on the rock with the words "my friend has saved my life". When he saw that, his friend began to be surprised and asked his friend. Why when I slapped you away and wrote on the ground and now that you were saved from the ground that pulled you, you then chiseled on the rock? His friend quickly answered, he meant that when someone did something bad to you, write it on the sand so that it would be quickly erased by the wind, but if someone helps you or does something good for you, then write him on a stone so that the wind won't erase him.

When the short story was finished by the teacher, the students were touched and said it was very impressive. On the other hand, the researcher saw how the students calmly and comfortably paid attention to the stories told by their teachers. Then several words phrases were written by the teacher on the board representing feelings such as condolences, anger and disappointment.

Condolences
I'm sorry to hear that!
I would like to express deepest condolences

Angry
I'm really angry
I cannot take this anymore

Disappointed
I'm so disappointed
You have let me down

The students were told by the teacher to focus on the existing phrases as new vocabulary, and then the students were divided into eight groups with an average of six to seven people in one group. The eight groups are further divided into two broader game rules, one as the government and the other as the seller of rice. The procedure of each group has been explained by their teacher and the rules of discussion and activity are full questions. In this learning process, students seemed to enjoy learning. For those students, it is a learning process that provides a good experience for them and their friends.

a. Data analysis

For data analysis, the researcher used a logical approach because the method used by the researcher was qualitative. Researchers do not use statistical formulas because what is used to analyze is qualitative. Researchers only try to analyze data by validity and quality as a result of the research. Therefore, the researcher analyzes all the data obtained from his research, and then takes data that supports the title of his research and ignores unused data but is not discarded because unused data will become an attachment.

There are two data classified by the researcher, namely:

- 1). Data that have a relationship with the learning and teaching process
- 2). Data that have a relationship with aspects that affect the learning and learning process.

To encourage students' abilities, SMAN.1 Ciputat has several programs in class X. The first program is a bilingual system. The Bilingual system program aims to developmental and self-confidence in students. The second program is the study club. This program aims to provide a positive response to speaking as well as to prepare students to refer to competition and overcome fear when speaking in front of classrooms and other open spaces. Another program is that schools try to facilitate their students by writing to be sent to various media such as newspapers, magazines and others.

From the description of the learning and teaching process above the researcher classifies these aspects into processes that have a relationship with Communicative Language Teachings such as cooperation that exists in groups, teachers as facilitators and students are more active in speaking or conveying ideas.

b. Teaching problems of Communicative Language Teaching on Vocabulary

There are several problems found by researchers in evaluating the teaching process carried out by teachers to their students. The problems are as follows:

- Students' ability to understand the language
- Lack of learning time and the commotion that occurs in the classroom

However, researchers have found a solution so that the above problems can be resolved based on the results of interviews with the English teacher and the two students in grades X4 and X6.

First, for us to understand students' abilities in English, students must be allowed to learn English. Students who are slow in understanding English must be continuously motivated so that their abilities can improve due to learning. Students who do not understand what the teacher says ask the teacher to repeat or give instructions so that the explanation is repeated. That was the answer given by the English teacher. While the answers of the two students were for students who lacked vocabulary, the teacher should give practical assignments on vocabulary using the English vocabulary test to improve the vocabulary skills of the students.

Second, to avoid shortages of time and noise in the classroom, the teacher should have prepared the materials in advance so that the time has been set accordingly and only certain voices come out responding to fellow students in communicating or discussing.

c. The advantages of teaching Vocabulary through Communicative Language Teaching

Some of the advantages of Vocabulary teaching through Communicative Language Teaching are as follows:

- Increased student motivation
- Promotes learning
- Emphasizes the communication process
- In a psycholinguistic perspective based on the acuity of communication

Based on the explanations above, the previous researchers concluded that teaching using Communicative Language Teaching for Vocabulary cannot run alone. This means that Vocabulary teaching must be included with other skills such as listening, reading, writing and speaking to help students understand the process of learning Vocabulary on Communicative Language Teaching. Therefore, the same thing was conveyed by Widdowson (1978) that "What the learners need to know how to do is to compose in the act of writing, comprehend in the act of reading, and to learn techniques of reading by writing and techniques of writing by reading."

Table of Communicative Language Teaching on Vocabulary

No.	Other skills	Vocabulary scores and other skills
1.	Vocabulary	20
2.	Reading	20
3.	Writing	20
4.	Speaking	20
5	Listening	20
	Total	100

4.1.2 Yiwey Wu (2009)

Wu researched on September 3, 2009, at a college study in China. He stated that the problems that often occur in the communication process are always mixing up languages. Therefore, language often experiences a setback because it does not use the correct words to communicate.

Related to what Wu found above, several techniques can be applied by the Communicative Language Teaching approach to Vocabulary teaching as follows:

4.1.2.1 Selection of topics that match the theme

This technique uses a textbook. This technique is certain that in the College English textbook there are several chapters to be studied, so they only choose which chapters to choose to discuss. However, before which chapter will be chosen, the teacher must first explain the chapter, starting from articulation, structure, part of speech and speech. Then the text of the book consists of several themes that will be chosen to be their discussion material. Supposed, they chose the first chapter on growing up. In that chapter, the teacher has again selected the topics that will be discussed by the students so that each student has experience or knowledge about growing up. The teacher then instructs the students to prepare their results and start presenting them. Thus, the relationship between the words used can run as desired and does not experience obstacles or confusion in communicating.

4.1.2.2 Explain the meaning of the word according to the situation

Following this technique, we know that the nature of speaking must go through speaking guidance as well. If students want to be able to speak well, they must be guided so that the language used is what is expected together. In communicating, the teacher must also see the desires of students related to the conditions to be discussed so that they can be actively involved. If the communication process is not by the wishes of the students, the communication process is likely ineffective due to the lack of student involvement in a communication. So what will be taught by the teacher, especially what must be considered is the meaning of the words conveyed and how he can attract students' interest and passion in communicating and motivate them about the importance of communicating properly and correctly. There are two ways that Wu conveyed to arouse students' desire for communication, namely:

a. Role-play

Role-play is to present context and real situations that occur in the classroom. This is important because it provides more opportunities for students to communicate socially and also the language used by students is easier based on their context, situation, mood and attitudes.

b. Reading authentic materials

Authentic reading of this material provides direct experience for students in communicating like a native speaker. Based on experience in speaking because they use their language in

conveying their ideas about the material they are learning. Based on the materials mentioned by Tomlinson are such as; newspaper articles, magazines, train tickets, airport announcements, advertisements, letters and more. An example of an advertising visit is for example about jeans. The comfort of using jeans in work because it damages the skin because they are made of quality fabrics and protect our skin as users are also collaborated with several colors to add to the uniqueness of these pants. The value of these pants is good for us to use in various events and does not suffer damage if long stored in the wardrobe and so on. From the description above, students easily convey their ideas on how to use the right words to be used and then conveyed by them as a result of their learning.

4.1.2.3. Read intensively

The purpose of language teaching is to develop students' abilities in both speaking and writing English. In this development, students can bring articles, for example, from magazines or newspapers to read to increase their vocabulary. by reading like that, students are followed by reading authentically. The authentic reading of students can vary, for example, literacy books, books about life and also books about education. After completing the new words found, students will experience progress and while waiting for the end of the lesson the teacher should have given instructions related to authentic reading being taught. Then, it will be effective in the way the teacher teaches.

The conclusion brought by Wu is that any teaching method that uses Communicative Language Teaching on Grammar, listening, reading, writing and others will be nothing if it is not accompanied by Vocabulary. As a teacher, it is very significant if you use a communicative approach to help increase students' awareness of communication and student learning abilities as well as broaden their horizons in Vocabulary. Not only enhancing vocabulary but also other skills such as writing, reading listening and speaking will improve by themselves because they are related.

Table of contents of the CLT approach to Vocabulary and other skills:

No.	Other skills	scores of Vocabulary and other skills
1.	Vocabulary	20
2.	Reading	20
3.	Writing	20
4.	Speaking	20
5	Listening	20
	Total	100

Vocabulary is the primary knowledge that must be learned in order for communication to be effective. However, other skills such as listening, reading, speaking writing must also be accompanied so that the vocabulary used is not carelessly spoken by the speaker and is also misunderstood by the listener. So, all the existing skills cannot stand alone to form a sentence. Therefore, according to the results found by the two researchers above, it can be said that the teaching of Communicative Language Teaching on Vocabulary cannot stand

alone because it needs each other to develop between other skills. The development of other skills also requires the Vocabulary as another value booster as an additional skill.

To better understand the relationship between these skills, we can refer to the tables that have been triggered in the two studies related to the predetermined value. These values are taken based on the attachment of all the skills above, if one skill is not included, then the teaching of the Communicative Language Teaching approach is not effective because it does not meet the effectiveness number.

4.1.3 Jue Xie (2010)

Xie researched in 2010 on Communicative Language Teaching on Vocabulary learning in Sweden. This study involved the seventh grade at Kristianstad Southern Swedish with a total sample of twenty students consisting of 6 girls and 16 boys aged 12-14 years. Apart from having the ability to use their first language, Swedish, they also learn English as their second language which they learn twice a week. In addition to the sample taken from students, data was also obtained by Je Xia through their English language teacher who came from China.

4.1.3.1 Observation of the main steps in the lesson

There are several main observations made by Xie in the process of learning English, namely:

1. Introduction

First, the teacher first introduces himself to the students because this is their first meeting so that before starting the learning process he must introduce himself to the students. The introduction took about 2-3 minutes so that their communication felt more relaxed to learn together. But besides that, there are still students who feel nervous when communicating with the teacher.

2. Presentation 1

The lesson begins with presenting in class with Unit Seven where words are mentioned, from palms to nails. The teacher uses some basic skills to impart new knowledge by showing concrete objects and demonstrating his body parts. He pronounced every word and offered comprehension checks to ascertain whether these students easy to understood or not. He also asked to clarify something that was not understood in the teaching process. When some students mispronounce it, the teacher makes patient corrective feedback to help them master the words.

3. Pair-work

In this step, students are asked to describe according to the shape of their hand which consists of five objectives used, namely philosophic, psychic, active, elementary and conic. Students will describe all the objects in a way to communicate and discover new vocabulary. After that students will be divided into several groups and three of them are asked to come to the front of the classroom to present their work. When they come forward and present their work, the teacher should not first correct what

was presented so that the learning process is disrupted and the communication built by them continues without fear of errors in communication. After they finished presenting, the atmosphere would feel more relaxed and the students who previously felt nervous would disappear instantly because they had been carried away by the atmosphere together in communicating.

4. Presentation 2.

The teaching content has temporarily returned to provide six new abstract words: regulation, analysis, fate, trade, rules and tools. This time the teacher adopts another skill to teach new words. The teacher asks his students to look up new words in the dictionary. Most of the students followed the activities according to the teacher's instructions, but one student did nothing. The teacher asks if he brought a dictionary or not, but he remains silent. The observation results showed that many students were willing to take part in these activities. When they understood the meaning of the words, they looked happy on their faces. The teacher also offers comprehension checks and makes requests to students. But in terms of regulation, although there are examples of legal phrases or customs that guide or control behavior or actions; decisions made by an organization, about what should or shouldn't be done. The expressions on the students' faces showed that they were still confused by the meaning, but the teacher did not explain further but instead he moved on to the next step.

5. Role-play

The next stage is the role-playing. The teacher designs a communicative activity for students to learn two adjectives-impulsive, bad-tempered words to consolidate what they have learned in Presentation 1, pair-work, Presentation 2 and develops their communicative skills. He explained to the students the exact explanation of the two words used to describe people's personalities. Before giving an assignment, he told his students what the situation should predict. The fate of partners: one acts as a fortune teller, the other as a customer; students choose their partners freely; fortune-tellers predict future events for customers, some words in role-play should be related to the words they have learned in the lesson. Then most students participate actively in the role-play. After they finished doing the role-playing, many couples volunteered to demonstrate their appearance in front of the class. After the role-play, students' anxiety and tension were greatly reduced from their facial expressions and behavior. Teachers and students are familiar with each other now.

6. Homework

That is the last stage of the lesson. The teacher assigns homework to his students. To consolidate what they have learned in class and review students' past tenses in learning. It only took about a minute to deliver.

4.1.3.2 Analysis and discussing

In this section, English learning will be carried out by the English teacher who comes from China intending to apply CLT in the learning process comprehensively in the classroom. Then the effectiveness of the learning process using CLT as has been previously observed related to the results of dictation and interviews with teachers rather than students.

a. Vocabulary learning strategy

There are three Vocabulary teaching strategies, namely:

1. Basic skills

In meetings 1 and 2, the teacher will teach ten new vocabulary words that have been instructed by the researcher for addition as the second language of the researcher and the theory of Vocabulary teaching and learning.

2. Presentation 1

At the beginning of presentation 1, the teacher will mention one concrete noun-inkpad while showing concrete objectives. Then he only pronounced the word. Students will recite the same word when it is their turn to pronounce it. Examples of teaching are as follows:

Example 1:

T: What is this, S1, do you know (while showing the inkpad to the students)?

S1: umm, it's inkpad.

T: Good! It's an inkpad. Well, now repeat after I mentioned the word inkpad.

All Ss: inkpad-inkpad (loudly)

T: I-n-k-p-a-d. Repeat after me.

Ss: I-n-k-p-a-d (loudly)

Boy A: Inkpad (clear pronunciation)

Boy B: Inkpad (clear pronunciation)

All girls: Inkpad (clear pronunciation)

All boys: Inkpad (clear pronunciation)

When teaching the word, the teacher teaches its spelling on the blackboard so that all aspects including speaking, writing and conceptual meanings can be presented to the students.

He proposed his understanding to his students to check whether the students understood or did not understand. For example, she found a man from the Eastern State who immigrated two years ago, and had been teaching English for two years but still couldn't pronounce any new vocabulary, so she helped by giving the man feedback.

Example 2:

T: The boy, please pronounce this word-Inkpad
 The boy: Sorry I don't know.
 T: Ok, take it easy. Look at my mouth and read after me Inkpad (slowly but clearly)
 A boy: inkpad (better than the first time but still not clear).
 T: uh, good. Read after me again, you will be better the next time.
 A boy: Inkpad (quite clear)
 T: Very good (thumbs up)

First, it is a modified type of interaction-comprehension checks, slower speech rate and how to use the thumb movements which are necessary and useful for the man's use.

Second, palm, thumb and nail which were presented. In this teaching process, the teacher teaches by moving his body parts. Conversation between teachers and students is the process of teaching nail words.

Example 3

T: What is this boys and girls (showing her ten red nails to pupils)
 Girl A: Nail. My mom has red nails
 Ss: (laugh)
 T: Yes you are right. Its nail (laugh too). Read after me.
 Girl A: Nail, n-a-i-l, nail Ss: Nail, n-a-i-l
 Girl B: me (stand up and laugh). I have pink nails.
 T: Oh good. Do you have colorful; l nails, a boy? All: (Laugh)
 Boy A: No, no, only girls have colorful nail (laughs and shakes his head).

3. Presentation 2

Regarding words - analyzing, organizing, fate, trading, tools and rules, the teacher uses other skills to look up words in the dictionary. Abstract words in English cannot be shown through simple body language or displayed through pictures, but the teacher cannot explain the words in Swedish. Fortunately, the Swedish student's standard of English is medium. They have learned many English words and basic sentence structures, which offers the possibility for the teacher to use a dictionary to define new words using other familiar words or to include them in English explanations where other words are in the sentence. is already displayed.

The teacher also has to understand these words to simplify their explanation even though it is the first meeting between the students and the words. This means that the words must be explained as clearly as possible so that they can be easily understood by students. Otherwise, students will be confused with the true meaning of the words. So, if students are asked to look for these meanings in the dictionary they only find the basic meaning without looking further the meaning of the words.

Example 4:

T: Now, open your dictionary; look for the word –tool boys and girls. I will give you five minutes and when you find it please explain to me the definition of the word.

Five minutes later, an explanation of the word tool was found from the dictionary of the respective students. The following is a dialogue between students and teachers:

Example 5:

T: Can you explain the meaning of the word tool S1?

S1: Yes, I can. This means that something is held in the hand and used by workers, such as gardeners and carpenters.

T: Now do you understand the meaning of the words boy and girl? Many

Ss: Yes (nods).

T: Then what is the tool? Who can give me an example?

S 2: Machine (hands up).

T: Great example, any other?

S 3: Scissors (raise hands).

S 4: Knife, brush.

S 5: Chainsaw.

T: Good, very good, you are right. Tool means something is used by workers.

The dialogue above shows that many students have understood the meaning of the tool words with the help of a dictionary. The next word is destiny. This time, he taught a new word by including it in an English explanation where the other words in the sentence were already displayed. The students were asked to provide example sentences for the word-destiny as well as its basic definition. The dialogue between teachers and students is as follows:

Example 6:

T: Boy A, now can you tell me the basic definition and example sentences or phrases of the word destiny?

Boy A: Ok um (pause) the definition is an event that will happen in the future. Uh, for example, he dreams of becoming a musician, but fate decides in other ways. (The teacher writes down definitions and example sentences on the board.)

T: Very good. Boy B, do you understand what boy A said?

Boy B: Yes.

T: And you, Girl A? Girl A: En (nods).

T: Ok, so here's another new word -a destiny that we want to learn today. He also used the traditional but still effective way of repetition in Presentation 2 because every word he met was not enough to memorize it.

Example 7:

T: Please read it after analyzing (clearly and aloud).

Ss: Analysis (out loud).

T: Now, students, rules

Boy: Analysis (out loud).
T: Girls, this time, rules.
Girl: Analysis (somewhat vague).
T: Aha, boys are better than girls.

In short, in Presentations 1 and 2, using the three basic skills of displaying concrete objects, displaying parts of the body and looking up words in the dictionary, the teacher taught the students ten new words and made a good start for the following communicative activity.

4. Contextualization

Finocchiaro and Brumfit (in Xia 2010: 28) state that learning words are not only studying linguistic forms. More importantly, second language learners must know how to use these words in communication. That is, the situational context must be considered in the mastery of a second language because it provides clues to the meaning of new words outside the linguistic system, thus helping students to learn words that are appropriate to a particular context.

Guided by the main feature of CLT, the teacher designs authentic communicative activities for students - describing the shape of the student's hand to his partner. Before he declares pair work, he gives a clear and concise explanation of the four new words. Then students are allowed to talk about the shape of their hands to their partners. Many students are highly motivated because it is in real situations which greatly arouse their communicative desires. Their attention is focused on the situational use of what is said or written. They deal with multiple languages, not just forms of the spelling or grammatical usage. They are very active in discussing the shape of each other's hands. Two pairs selected from the pair work are analyzed and discussed as follows:

Pair 1:

Boy A: Hello, B (shakes hands with B).
Boy B: Hi, show me your right hand.
Boy A: Um, your right hand is a cone (clear pronunciation).
Boy B: No... (Pauses) I don't think so. It's basic (clear pronunciation).
Boy B: Oh, maybe I did something wrong.

The two boys talked about each other's hand shapes fluently and their pronunciation was correct. That is, they not only master the linguistic forms of the two words but also can use the target language appropriately in a particular context. That is, their communicative competence is developed through authentic communicative activities. They do not learn to deliberately form the words. Instead, they are integrated into this situation and naturally acquire the target language. Master praised them for their good performance just in time after their performance was over.

Pair 2:

Girl A: B, can you tell me my hand shape?
Girl B: Eh, which one? Girl A: Right.

Girl B: Um, this is philosophic.

Girl A: Yes, I think so, philosophical (clear pronunciation). How about you. Let me see.

Girl B: Yeah, it's conical, oh, no, no, sorry, square, square. Square (unclear pronunciation).

Girl A: You're right.

5. Role-play

To master the two new adjectives-impulsive and bad-tempered, to consolidate what they learned in Presentation 1, 2 and pair work, the teacher designed a role-play. Before giving assignments, the teacher explains the meaning of the two adjectives clearly and concisely. Then he retreated, speaking less, only observing the appearance of his students. Instead, students become the centre of the class and play a major role in communicative activities. They participate actively in role-playing. The teacher walks between the groups during their preparation sometimes offering advice and assistance. About twelve minutes later, many couples raised their hands and volunteered to demonstrate their appearance in front of the whole class. Here, the two selected pairs are analyzed and discussed as follows:

Pair 3:

B 1: Hi, are you interested in your upcoming event?

B 2: Of course. Can you tell me about my upcoming event?

B 1: Uh, yeah, it's free. Please show me your right palm.

B 2: OK (laughs and show right hand to S 1).

B1: Aha, the shape of your hands is basic, uh; you're impulsive, bad-tempered. You will have three marriages and you will die for seventy years (laughs).

B 2: Oh my God, that's impossible. You tricked me (laughs).

The whole process is consistent. Four new words-palms, active, impulsive, bad-tempered are used in role-playing. Communicative competence in using the target language for proper communication is acquired naturally in communication. Apart from mastering knowledge of the target language and practicing their communicative skills, the two boys developed their imaginations. Besides, when the two boys appeared in front of the class, they sometimes made gestures and put on funny faces. An atmosphere of relaxation, harmony and fun prevails in the classroom. The teacher and all students feel close and do not feel alien to each other as in Presentations 1 and 2. They do a good job.

4.1.3.3. Conclusion

Guided by a relevant theoretical background, the study consisting of observation of English lessons, dictation and interviews show that compared to Grammar-Translation Method, Communicative Language Teaching based on many modern humanistic and communicative theories is effective in teaching and learning English vocabulary in many aspects:

1. In CLT classes, many vocabularies are no longer taught in the form of isolated word lists but are taught in an authentic context. Vocabulary teaching focuses on

- developing communicative skills rather than regulating the form of the target language.
2. CLT makes students acquire vocabulary knowledge naturally, rather than learning on purpose. Besides, the modified target language input obtained from the interaction between the teacher and students allows them to gain a better understanding of vocabulary knowledge.
 3. CLT promotes the communicative competence of learners and stimulates their inner motivation because communicative activities are close and relevant to their daily lives.
 4. CLT can make students take responsibility for their learning and encourages them to find the form and structure of the target language for themselves.
 5. CLT encourages the development of a teamwork spirit of students through communicative activities and fosters the individuality of students by expressing their different views and ideas freely in conversational interactions between them

4.1.4 Sri Endang Kusmaryati 2018

This research was conducted by Kusmaryati in 2018. She said that before using the teaching process in the classroom, teachers should prepare learning designs according to the current curriculum so that teaching is in line with common desires. When the teaching is running, the teacher should guide the students to achieve good results as well.

This teaching model has an attachment to teaching that is environmental and experiential in an instructional manner such as giving ideas, summaries or traits. It can also provide theories, frameworks, patterns or examples for educational-curricular components such as teaching techniques, classroom learning plans, group instruction and so on.

This teaching and learning model is a critical instructional plan and an intermediary to assist educators in developing the abilities of their students.

As expressed by Kusmaryati in her journal, the purpose of teaching English as a foreign language is to help improve communicative skills, both writing and speaking. In improving the students' abilities, the teacher is not only ready to provide various abilities related to language (grammar skills) but the teacher only provides abilities related to how students communicate (communicative abilities) so students will automatically experience improvements in those skills too. By using this communicative approach, students will be able to analyze all the words without having to use grammar skills.

A classroom is a place for communication between students and teachers. Communicative vocabulary teaching can be effective in the classroom when the approach teacher uses interactive activities. The teacher can act as a facilitator and monitor and teach Vocabulary to students through interactive games. By using through interactive activities, the teacher must see that students must use new vocabulary and must understand the meaning of the words and

put it into practice. The teacher can also use pictures to discover new vocabulary and to explain to them both in pronunciation and spelling.

The Communicative Teaching and learning model of Vocabulary through interactive activities can provide a great opportunity for students to be more active and help improve students' vocabulary skills.

There are three areas in the learning model of Communicative Teaching and Vocabulary

Learning through interactive activities carried out by previous researchers. The three learning models or steps are pre-teaching, whilst-teaching and post-teaching. Below is an example of a Communicative Teaching and Vocabulary learning model through interactive activities quoted directly from previous researchers without the slightest change in words from the observer. Kurmasyati (2018: 33-34):

Materials/Topic : I Love People around Me

Teaching Method : Scientific Learning Approach

A. Pre-teaching:

1. Greeting
2. Checking the attendance list
3. Checking the students' readiness
4. Giving the students motivation contextually related to the teaching materials and everyday life, by giving examples.
5. Asking about the relation between students' prior knowledge and the material learned.
6. Explaining the purpose of learning or basic competencies to achieve.

B. Whilst-teaching: (Applying interactive activities)

1. Observing:

- a. The students observe the image of "family tree" shown by the teacher.
- b. The students listen to the teacher explaining the image of "family tree".

- c. The students complete the identity format based on information obtained from the image of "family tree" that has been described.
2. Questioning: With the guidance and direction of the teacher, the students ask questions about the pictures of "family tree", as well as other things that they want to know.
3. Exploring / Experimenting:
 - a. The class is divided into groups of four.
 - b. Students receive a distribution of tasks from teachers containing a vocabulary of "family" in English and Indonesian differently for each group. (Matching Game)
 - c. The students find the appropriate vocabulary words from English to Indonesian contained in the text in groups.
4. Associating: With the help of the media shown by the teacher, the students identify the results of the group discussion.
5. Communicating:
 - a. Two of the students (representative of the group) come forward trying to use the media to describe the materials
 - b. The teacher gives feedback about the concept of the materials being studied.
6. Creating:

The teacher gives guided, semi-guided, or free productions tasks to the students to create a text.

C. Post-teaching:

1. The students and teacher reflect on the learning activities.
2. The students and teacher provide feedback on the process and learning outcomes.
3. The teacher and students make a summary of the materials that have been studied.
4. The teacher gives information about the plan of learning activities for the next meeting.

English is a language that is learned not as a second language, but as a foreign language. The purpose of learning English is to be able to communicate with newcomers visiting Indonesia as tourists or in the form of cooperation between them.

Meanwhile, Vocabulary is one component of language teaching and is the most important rule in learning English because with vocabulary students' communication skills can improve.

Before carrying out the teaching and learning process in the classroom, teachers should have designed their teaching methods and learning principles according to the ongoing curriculum so that they can guide the learning, teaching and assessment process for students in order to get satisfactory results.

4.1.5 Lilik Yuliawati dan Aprillia (2019)

This research was conducted by Yuliawati and Aprillia using the action research method with the aim of encouraging students to solve problems and challenges from practicing and bringing them to better innovations. In this study, the participation required is 30 students from the Gama 88 Harapan Baru Elementary School Bekasi. Two classes that were included in this research, namely class A 15 students and class B 15 students with an average age of 11 to 12 years who studied English as a foreign language.

The data were collected by researchers by means of interviews, conversations and observations. Retrieval of data through conversations and interviews after meetings in the classroom with students by practicing Communicative Language Teaching using pictures and games which will coincide with data collection in the form of observations. To analyze the data, the following methods were used:

Data Reading → Data Selection → Data Presentation → Data Interpretation → Conclusion

4.1.5.1 Students' perceptions of traditional teaching methods before using CLT

However, previously the researcher first described the perceptions of vocabulary teaching carried out by the teacher using the traditional method through word lists and the use of dictionaries before using Communicative Language Teaching. The teacher tells students to memorize existing vocabulary, but students often consult the teacher how to find the meaning of a word in the dictionary and it is difficult to memorize the words in the word list.

The first step taken by the teacher was interviewing 30 students regarding their perceptions of teaching using this traditional method in learning vocabulary. The answers found were only 4 students 13% of students who answered did not have difficulty in learning. While 20 students or 64% of students said that they found it difficult to find the meaning of the word then it took time to find the meaning of the words and m, they also said that they were bored when learning using that method. Then 7 or 23% of the students said that they find it difficult to memorize words from the word list given by their teacher.

From the explanation above, it can be said that teaching using the word list method and using a dictionary is ineffective and it is easy to bore students in the learning process.

4.1.5.2 Vocabulary teaching using CLT

Pre-teaching is done by the teacher before starting the teaching process in the classroom. When learning wants to start, the teacher prepares the material or session in their meeting first and their lesson plans are by the learning rules. At this initial meeting, the materials to be studied are those related to animals and fruits. The lessons that will be used in the action research class are as follows:

In starting lessons, the teacher uses the class as the leader class. Chair arrangement which is an arrangement that is usually used directly to help each other, then students will stand up when appointed without any fear from the number of friends who are in them and expressly convey their work according to the learning time that has been arranged together.

Teaching Vocabulary through Communicative Language Teaching in elementary schools, the teacher only acts as a facilitator. One student will start to lead conversations with other students and then he will also act as an advisor in seeing the questions that will be asked by his friend. All the students in the room acted as speakers. They will interrupt each other and negotiate to understand the meaning of the words conveyed and provide explanations to their friends who do not understand the word when their friends' abilities are still unable to analyze.

This learning process has a series of actions that will be used so that the achievement of language understanding can be fulfilled. This time, the material that will be taught by the teacher is material related to animals and fruits. Then the learning process will begin when the teacher is in the classroom.

Below are the steps were taken by the teacher when entering the classroom to start the teaching and learning process:

1. Engage:

The first step; the teacher began to step into the classroom, greetings while walking cheerfully and smiling. It was a sign that class time was about to start. The teacher will ask a few questions according to the topic that will be studied by students.

T: OK, students, have you ever been to the zoo?

T: Do you have pets? Will you be willing to protect them? Can you name what animal you know?

S1: "Yes Miss"

S2: "Tiger Miss"

T: OK you are a smart student. So now we will learn about animal names in English, so I ask for your cooperation and attention

2. Study:

The second step: in this step the teacher will provide some information to the students in the form of new words and ask the students to repeat the words, learn and memorize them. The teacher will use tools such as picture media to show them. The picture will also appear an explanation, question or to explain something.

T: now we will learn about animals. There are two types of animals that we will study, namely domestic animals (tame animals) and wild animals, and then you will know which animals can fly, swim and walk. So, you name the animals that you know as much as possible. Now I have some pictures of animals

Figure A is the wild animals

1

2

3

"This is a lion"

"This is a wolf"

Simultaneously the students answered.

T: Now I want to ask you. What is this (while showing picture no.1)

S1: it is a tiger. Is this (while showing picture no.2)

S2: it's a lion. Is this? (Show image no.3)

S3: it is a wolf.

T: Very good kids. OK, I'll tell you about the wild animals. Wild animals usually live in grove forests or zoos. They are extremely dangerous and cannot be used as pets. So, now I will ask whether tigers can swim. If you say you can, then you must say you can. Tigers can swim"but if you say they cannot then you say that tigers cannot swim. Can lions swim?

Ss: No. Lions can't swim. T: Great! Now you can ask your friends.

S1: Can lion walk?

S2: Yes, you can. The lion can walk. Can tigers walk?

S3: Yes. Tigers can walk

T: Good. After the wild animals, I will also explain tame animals. Do you know what tame animal is? Tame animals are not dangerous. We can make them as pets. Can you mention the name of the animals?

Figure B is the tame animals:

1

2

3

T: I will name the animals in English then you repeat them after I mention them.

"This is a bull"

"This is a cow"

"This is a rabbit"

The third step: in this step the students are divided into groups, either in pairs or individually. When the teacher sees that the students are ready, the teacher will deliver a role-play and prepare the students to learn through games. Students will have more opportunities to learn new vocabulary that is conveyed by their peers. This learning process will also have a good effect on students' learning modality. During the learning process, the teacher will act as a monitor and be ready to provide feedback to them.

T: If you no longer have any questions from you, then we continue to learn by using games. Group will consist of two, namely group A and group B. If A is in charge of choosing an image, group B will be in charge of guessing how many letters are in the image. Write the wrong letters on the line provided above and give a value to the group that managed to answer correctly.

A: N how many letters are there?

B: There are 9 letters (while going forward and writing 9 flat lines on the board)

A: Does it fly?

B: Yes.

A: is there a letter T?

B: Yes. It is letter number 3 and 4

A: Is there a letter B?

B: Yes, it is the letter key of the first letter

T: that's right. Group A scores, now are the time for group B

B: How many letters are there?

A: There are 7 letters (group A forward and write 7 flat lines on the blackboard)

B: Can it fly?

A: No. It can't fly

B: Can it work?

A: Yes.

B: Is there an A?

A: No. There is no letter A.

B: Is there a letter B?

A: Yes. That is the first letter.

B: Is there an F too?

A: Yes. It is letter number 3 and 4

B: Buffalo.

In the first discovery, the material studied was the introduction of animal forms, both tame and wild animals. Then, in this second meeting, the material learned was the identification of fruits because students will be asked to name what fruits they like.

1. Engaged

T: Do you like to eat fruit? What fruit do you like?

2. Study:

T: OK, students, the material we are going to study today is material about fruits. Then I will show you some pictures related to fruits which will become a picture for you all. Therefore, I ask for your attention and concentration in this learning process.

Fruit image

T: Ok, my students ask you to repeat this reading after I read it.

- This is a Strawberry (while showing the picture)
- This is an orange (while showing the picture)
- This is an apple (while showing the picture)
- This is Banana (while showing the picture)

This is Apple (while showing the picture) I will ask you what fruit name you like and you can answer it using the sentence my favorite fruit is...

S1: My favorite fruit is oranges.

T: Very good. Now ask your friends.

S1: What is your favorite fruit?

S2: My favorite fruit is apples.

T: Very good! Ok, now I will ask you, for example, a banana. Do you like eating bananas? If you say like, then the answer is yes, I like to eat bananas.

However, if you don't like it then the answer is no. I don't like eating bananas.

Do you understand? So, let's start practicing: Do you like pineapples?

S1: Yes I do. I like to eat pineapple. Do you like to eat oranges?

S2: Yes. I like to eat oranges. How about you, do you like to eat grapes?

S3: No, I don't like to eat wine. do you like to eat apples

3. Activities

T: Ok students, next we will learn by playing games. in the game it will be divided into three groups. Are you ready?

Ss: Yes ma'am.

T: there are six letters and a yellow colour then this fruit is very liked by monkeys.

A: Banana fruit

T: For group B, there are six letters that are round in shape and rich in vitamin C. The name of this fruit is according to its colour.

B: Citrus fruit

T: It's time for group C. There are also six letters, small, round and have two colours, red and yellow.

C: Wine

4.1.5.3 The advantage of Vocabulary teaching through pictures and games using the CLT method

Vocabulary teaching using pictures and games is very effective. That is the answer to the results of the previous and research interview with the English language subject teacher. Then the answers from the students, they said that learning using pictures and games was not boring and made them very interested in the teaching and learning process.

a. Students' perceptions of the CLT teaching method through this graph

There were 18 students or 64% said that they understood vocabulary learning using CLT better than learning vocabulary through word lists and using an English dictionary. Then, 4 or 13% of students knew better when learning with the CLT method in terms of pronouncing words, understanding words, and it was easier for them to practice than using the long method. 8 or 27% of students said that learning using pictures and games was more interesting and relaxing than using old methods.

According to the results of the interview, it can be concluded by previous researchers that there are two. First, learning by using pictures and games really helps students to develop. By using pictures, students can easily analyze and encourage students to learn more because they use various kinds of pictures and moreover combine colours that are more stimulating to the students' brain analysis. The second is to use games. Games are also very helpful because students learn while refreshing and it doesn't make students feel bored in learning. It can make students more active because they have many opportunities to speak and be creative with the abilities they have based on their conditions.

There are also several other advantages of using the Communicative Language Teaching approach, namely:

- By enabling students to communicate in a very meaningful way when in a context that is prepared to communicate both to their group and other groups.
- Preparing speakers who can be adapted, from beginner speakers to advanced speakers, to interact together even though they have different language backgrounds but can use English.
- CLT allows the teacher to return to being a facilitator to observe students learning through text and respond directly to what the students need.
- CLT also emphasizes the meaning of language that students want to convey following their ideas and ideas.

4.1.5.4 Problems that occur in the learning and teaching process

Teaching English Vocabulary to Elementary School education is not easy for those who teach it. Teaching must require the ability to organize, handle and control strong so that the class remains by the applicable rules.

Most students mistakenly use language which is a varied language to convey their ideas; there are even students who act to help other friends to convey the meaning of what their friends have said. However, it is a natural thing in learning a language, because with these mistakes the language will naturally vary. Besides, the students were bored because they sat in the classroom for too long because of studying, the teacher invited the students to discuss so that the students did not just sit and listen to the teacher who was talking.

Another problem is when new words are heard by students and are not understood, they must first be explained by the teacher so that they can be understood by students and learning will go according to what is desired. It is one way in which students can follow subjects to be studied together. There is also another method that can be used by the teacher, namely drilling longer, but that method cannot be used by the teacher because the students will feel bored with the learning.

4.1.5.5 Conclusion

At first the students studied Vocabulary using the method of vocabulary lists and the use of a dictionary to increase their vocabulary. However, learning with the traditional method says students are very boring and difficult to understand and take up a lot of time in the learning process. On the other hand, the researcher applied the learning process using CLT to pictures and games in learning vocabulary. The teaching uses three elements, namely Engage, Study and Active Stage. Teaching using image media and games has several advantages, such as:

- Media can give a positive response because it can make students easily absorb the material presented by the teacher.
- Media can also make students study hard and make students not feel bored because it can be made funny by students in the process of stimulating and entertaining students in learning.

Besides that, Vocabulary teaching using the CLT method has several good advantages in student learning. CLT can make students improve their vocabulary and their pronunciation in communicating is improved by. The communication process of students can also be directed because of the meaning understood by fellow students when using English. CLT also adapts students in using English evenly when students have different language backgrounds - surgery.

However, some problems often occur in the learning process, for example when students get bored when they stay in the classroom for a long time to discuss. Then there are new vocabulary words that have just been heard by the students. Then it will also be difficult for students where the teacher has not explained the meaning of the words. So, the teacher should pay attention to all of these when starting the learning process in the classroom.

Table: 4.1.4.5.

No.	Vocabulary Teaching	Score
1.	Traditional methods (word list and dictionary)	0
2.	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)	50
3.	Pictures and Games	50

Therefore, the researcher used the table above to provide a little explanation related to the teaching effect of the Vocabulary learning process on CLT, which is the research objective of the researcher.

From the results seen in the table above, we can say that teaching using CLT through pictures and games is more effective than using traditional methods such as word lists and dictionaries.

4.2 Discussion

From the results listed in 4.1 above, research related to the use of Communicative Language Teaching in Vocabulary is minimal and rarely studied. Therefore, the researchers found only a few journal articles related to the research.

The results found by researchers were very different from previous researchers. Erwin (2008) states that teaching Communicative Language Teaching on vocabulary will not work effectively if it is not accompanied by other skills such as listening, reading, writing and speaking. These skills will help each other to smooth the speaker with the interlocutor because it helps the speaker to communicate both in writing and orally.

The same thing was also conveyed by Wu (2009) that the learning process using Communicative Language Teaching is very helpful for developing the abilities of other skills in learning languages. However, he also said that without using Vocabulary learning, other skills will not run smoothly even other skills are nothing without Vocabulary. Vocabulary is a basic skill that must be learned and understood because if you want to communicate, the first thing you must know is Vocabulary. From the neatly arranged vocabulary in the form of ideas and ideas to the formation of a sentence that the speaker wants to convey (Speaking) then it is captured, analyzed, and understood by the listener (Listening).

Meanwhile, Xia (2010) stated that teaching using Communicative Language Teaching is more effective and has many aspects compared to teaching the Grammar Translation Method. Suppose that CLT teaching no longer refers to target students. This means that the teacher no longer regulates how to use the grammar that must be used but provides more opportunities for students to speak following the context. Then students will indirectly capture and get new vocabulary without using vocabulary lists and dictionaries as tools to add their vocabulary. Besides that, students are automatically able to take actions communicatively and improve their target language both individually and in groups.

Kusmaryati (2018) stated that vocabulary learning is very important because to form sentences, the first thing that must be needed is vocabulary. He did not mention the relationship of vocabulary teaching with other skills, but he did mention that vocabulary is the most important component that must be learned for the communication process to run well. For grammar, it can be learned after enough vocabulary is formed into a sentence.

However, Yuliawati and Aprillia (2019) are more likely to use CLT against vocabulary through learning media such as pictures and games. According to them, using the media as a tool to apply CLT to vocabulary is more effective because students understand more easily and not when in the classroom because the teaching and learning process is ongoing. Students will be more creative because they have more time to communicate among themselves according to the context determined by their teacher. Therefore, according to the results found by researchers by what has been researched by previous researchers, teaching using CLT to Vocabulary has positive things because it has made good progress towards students' abilities. CLT learning of Vocabulary has progressed because it is seen from year to year that it has increased and this is evident in the journals that the researchers took to show above.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Conclusion

From the results of the research above, several advantages exist in teaching CLT to Vocabulary. Both advantages are the learning process using pictures and games as well as combining all existing skills to improve students' abilities, especially in the field of vocabulary.

However, CLT based learning towards vocabulary can be said that learning and teaching to use CLT is not effective for students without involving other skills such as Reading, Listening, Writing and Speaking as well as teaching aids such as pictures to describe what students want to describe. Students' vocabulary will be improved when using other skills as a means of adding to their vocabulary. With CLT, students can see how the communication process is used because the situation is used by the students to play the maximum possible role in communicating, so their students use the Speaking skill as the first skill and Listening as the second skill to capture and convey new vocabulary. Likewise with the image media that will be described by the students, what is needed is writing and reading skills to find and write new vocabulary that will be used to describe the image. So that, with these skills, the students' vocabulary will increase because all skills are active in their learning process.

All the skills in the language learning process are a link that cannot be separated from one another, because vocabulary is only based element in all of skills and it does not improve by itself without the intervention of other skills.

In terms of the learning process that took place during previous studies, it can be emphasized again that CLT teaching of Vocabulary has positive things even though some researchers say that teaching CLT to Vocabulary is nothing because all language skills are interrelated one another.

5.2. Suggestion

Previously, as stated by the researcher, the research related to CLT on Vocabulary was very minimal so that the researcher only found a few journal articles related to this study. So with the hope and suggestion that future researchers conduct more research related to the CLT teaching process of Vocabulary so that it will generate more new references that will serve as a reference for CLT learning of Vocabulary. Given that only a few researchers research to find out the CLT learning process of Vocabulary.

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